

"PRACTICE OF USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND INCREASING ITS EFFICIENCY"

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Abstract: *The article examines the main aspects of using digital technologies in teaching English. The main goal is to help teachers organize students' learning activities more effectively using modern digital tools, making learning English more interesting and interactive.*

Key words: *digital technology, English language teaching, educational learning, effectiveness, interactive learning.*

English is one of the most widely studied and used languages in the world, and its teaching is one of the most important areas of the modern education system today. [3] However, traditional teaching methods are sometimes not enough to maintain student interest and improve efficiency. Therefore, there is a need to integrate digital technologies into the English language teaching process. [6]

By integrating technology into the learning process and using such opportunities as online platforms, mobile applications and multimedia tools, it is possible to increase students' motivation and improve language learning results. It is emphasized that these methods can make a significant contribution to improving the effectiveness of teaching and the quality of the language learning process.

Today, digital technologies create opportunities to make the learning process more effective and interactive. [1] The student learning process will become more interesting and successful with the help of online platforms, mobile applications, video and audio materials. These tools help to create various forms of learning, which allows you to take into account the diversity of student learning styles. For example, visual, auditory and kinesthetic elements can be used to deepen understanding of the material and increase student engagement.

In addition, technology allows you to implement an individual approach, taking into account the characteristics of each student. Self-study programs such as mobile apps provide students with the opportunity to study at their own time and pace, without being limited by traditional classroom settings. This way, students can improve their skills at their own pace, which helps them learn more deeply. Technology also allows for regular monitoring of student progress, giving both teachers and students the opportunity to make timely adjustments to the learning process.

The use of digital tools helps increase student motivation, as many online resources offer fun and game-like elements that make learning more interesting and accessible. Programs and platforms such as Duolingo or Quizlet provide various forms of exercises and tests that help learn vocabulary and grammar in a game format, making the learning process less formal and more engaging.

In addition, the widespread adoption of distance learning during the pandemic has further increased the importance of digital technologies in teaching. The effective use of digital tools has created new opportunities for teachers and students to continue the learning process. [5] In the context of restrictions caused by the pandemic, digital technologies have become an essential tool for maintaining the educational process. Online classes, webinars, and video conferences have allowed teachers to stay in touch with students, providing them with the necessary knowledge and support. To improve the effectiveness of English language teaching, it is necessary, first of all, to improve the qualifications of teachers and provide them with modern teaching methods. In addition, it is important to adapt teaching materials and methods to modern requirements, increase students' motivation and stimulate their interest in learning English.

Distance learning has also highlighted the importance of digital literacy among both teachers and students. In the context of distance education, it was necessary to teach students how to effectively use various educational platforms, as well as develop their skills in independently searching for and working with educational materials on the Internet.

At the same time, an in-depth study of the experience and methodological approaches to using digital technologies in education has become an urgent task.[4] Many studies are now aimed at understanding how to integrate various digital resources into educational programs, how to correctly evaluate the effectiveness of these technologies, and how they can be used to improve the quality of education.

Digital technologies also create opportunities for global communication, which is an important element in teaching English. Online platforms such as Tandem or HelloTalk give students the chance to communicate with native speakers, which significantly improves their practical skills. Virtual exchanges, participation in online courses and forums allow students to immerse themselves in the language environment, which is an integral part of effective learning. Therefore, the use of digital technologies in teaching English and increasing their effectiveness is of great importance today to ensure the successful learning of students. The benefits of these technologies are obvious and they provide new opportunities for a personalized

approach to learning, improving the quality and accessibility of education, as well as creating a motivating and dynamic educational environment.

The main objective of this study is to explore and analyze methods for the effective use of digital technologies in English language teaching. The study examines how digital technologies can improve students' English language learning, their impact on the learning process, and their role in creating new opportunities for teachers and students.

The importance of improving the pedagogical and methodological skills of teachers was emphasized. For effective work of a teacher in the educational process it is necessary to have sufficient knowledge of modern teaching methods. In addition, it is necessary to organize trainings, courses, seminars to familiarize teachers with modern pedagogical methods and technologies. This showed the importance of adaptation to international standards and requirements when teaching English in related language schools. This will help to create simpler and more effective opportunities for students to learn the language, as well as adapt the education system to global requirements.

The following methods were used in the study such as surveys, experiment and evaluation. Surveys were conducted among teachers and schoolchildren. Surveys were used to study the level of perception of digital technologies by schoolchildren and their attitude towards them. Practical classes were conducted with schoolchildren using various digital technologies (online platforms and mobile applications) in teaching English. During the experiment, schoolchildren were divided into different groups and their academic performance was assessed.

Evaluation of the impact of digital technologies on the learning process by analyzing the responses of students and teachers. This method reveals the positive and negative aspects of using technologies.

The study confirmed the effectiveness of using digital technologies in teaching English and gave the following results. Firstly, increasing motivation, applications such as Duolingo increased students' interest, making the learning process interactive and fun. [2] Secondly, it gave an individual approach, using platforms such as Moodle, each student was given an individual approach and their level of development was monitored. It should be noted that audio and video materials were effective in improving students' pronunciation and listening development, and digital technologies increased students' English proficiency and made the learning process more effective. But, sometimes there were technical problems, such as internet connection.

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of using digital technologies in teaching English. With the help of digital platforms and mobile applications, students' motivation increased and their English proficiency improved. The technologies also provided students with an individual approach and helped them develop their pronunciation and listening skills. However, during the study, technical problems such as internet speed and difficulties in setting up programs arose. In order to fully utilize the potential of digital technologies in the future, it is necessary to improve the digital competencies of teachers and to improve the technical infrastructure.

Adaptation to international practice and standards is one of the most important areas of teaching English. The introduction of these principles in schools where instruction is conducted in related languages will contribute to improving the quality of education and student achievement. The results of the study also show that the introduction of modern technologies, innovative methods and pedagogical innovations in teaching English allows us to adapt to global educational standards, improve the educational process and increase students' interest in the language.

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